

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Substituted 5-Hydrothiazolo(4,3-b)-1,3,4-oxa(thia)diazoles and 5-Hydrothiazolo(3,4-b)-1,2,4-triazoles

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Six 2-aryl-3-(3-arylthioureido)-4-thiazolidinones (III) were prepared by addition-condensation of mercaptoacetic acid to aldehyde 4-arylthiosemicarbazones (II). 5-Aryl-2-arylamino-5-hydrothiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (IV), the corresponding thiazolo [4,3-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (V) and 1,5-diaryl-5-hydro-2-mercaptothiazolo[3,4-b]-1,2,4-triazoles (VI) were obtained by cyclisation of III with conc. H_2SO_4 , I_2 -KI/NaOH and NaOH, respectively. Compounds III-VI were compared with Dithane M-45 for their fungitoxicity against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari*. The screening results have been correlated with the structural features of the tested compounds.

ENCOURAGED by the significant fungitoxicity displayed by a number of heterocyclic systems containing bridgehead nitrogen atom reported earlier^{1,2}, we considered it of interest to fuse the biolabile thiazole nucleus with biologically versatile rings like 1,3,4-oxa(thia)diazole and 1,2,4-triazole with a view of obtaining fungicides of high potency. The synthetic approach to the title compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Addition-condensation of mercaptoacetic acid to aldehyde 4-arylthiosemicarbazones (II) furnished the substituted 4-thiazolidinones (III). III were cyclised with conc. H_2SO_4 , I_2 -KI/NaOH and NaOH to furnish the corresponding thiazolo [4,3-b]-1,

3,4-thiadiazoles (IV), thiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (V) and thiazolo[3,4-b]-1,2,4-triazoles (VI), respectively.

The synthesised compounds were characterised by their ir spectra and elemental analyses. The ir spectra of 3-(3-arylthioureido)-4-thiazolidinones (III) revealed strong band around 1700 cm^{-1} ($\nu C=O$), a medium band near 3320 cm^{-1} (νNH) and bands around 1480 and 1185 cm^{-1} ($\nu C=S$). Disappearance of $\nu C=O$ band in the ir spectra of compounds IV-VI is compatible with their assigned structures. Further, the compounds IV and V exhibited a weak ir band around 3300 cm^{-1} attributable to νNH . The compounds VI were devoid of any νNH band but showed a weak band near 2550 cm^{-1} due to νSH . In addition, all the compounds revealed ir absorption bands due to substituted benzene nuclei in the expected regions.

The antifungal activity of compounds III-VI was evaluated against *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* at three concentrations (Table 2). In general, compounds IV-VI were more potent than their parent 4-thiazolidinones (III). The compounds IVf, VI, VIe and VIf displayed fungitoxicity of the order of a commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 at 1000 ppm but their activity decreased considerably at lower concentrations (100 and 10 ppm).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (in KBr) were recorded on a Hitachi-295 spectrophotometer.

4-Arylthiosemicarbazides (I)³: These were prepared by following the method of Kazakov and Postovskii. Aromatic amine (0.1 mole) in ammonia

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TABLE 1—YIELDS, MELTING POINTS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS III-VI

Compound	Ar	Ar'	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
						Nitrogen	Sulphur
2-Aryl-3-(3-arylthioureido)-4-thiazolidinones (III)							
IIIa	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	60	195	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	12.97 (12.24)	18.97 (18.66)
b	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	59	120-121	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	11.03 (11.13)	16.82 (16.95)
c	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	68	140-142	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	12.32 (12.24)	18.52 (18.66)
d	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	63	127	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	11.06 (11.13)	16.86 (16.95)
e	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	57	195-197	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS ₂	11.44 (11.55)	17.68 (17.61)
f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	62	191	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS ₂	10.68 (10.55)	16.02 (16.08)
5-Aryl-2-arylamino-5-hydrothiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (IV)							
IVa	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	81	143-145	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	13.05 (12.93)	19.61 (19.69)
b	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	70	136	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	11.72 (11.68)	17.94 (17.80)
c	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	86	255-257	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	12.83 (12.92)	19.76 (19.69)
d	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	76	123-124	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	11.81 (11.68)	17.89 (17.80)
e	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	72	195-196	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	12.12 (12.16)	18.43 (18.55)
f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	82	178	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂	11.23 (11.05)	16.72 (16.84)
5-Aryl-2-arylamino-5-hydrothiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (V)							
Va	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	48	92	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	13.43 (13.59)	10.46 (10.35)
b	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	53	117	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS	12.28 (12.23)	9.26 (9.31)
c	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	56	71-72	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	13.47 (13.59)	10.41 (10.35)
d	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	51	215-217	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS	12.31 (12.23)	9.22 (9.31)
e	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	57	143	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ OS	12.65 (12.74)	9.85 (9.71)
f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	52	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	11.68 (11.54)	8.93 (8.79)
1,5-Diaryl-5-hydro-2-mercaptothiazolo[3,4-b]-1,2,4-triazoles (VI)							
VIa	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	61	71-72	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	12.96 (12.88)	19.54 (19.63)
b	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	58	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	11.54 (11.65)	17.89 (17.75)
c	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	68	94-96	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	12.92 (12.88)	19.77 (19.63)
d	<i>o</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	57	81	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	11.51 (11.65)	17.63 (17.75)
e	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	68	170	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ S ₂	12.02 (12.15)	18.48 (18.52)
f	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	56	138	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ S ₂	11.17 (11.05)	16.67 (16.84)

(25 ml, sp. gr. 0.88) was treated with CS₂ (10 ml), sodium chloroacetate (0.1 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (10 ml, 50%), successively. The 4-arylthiosemicarbazide thus prepared were recrystallised from EtOH.

Aldehyde 4-arylthiosemicarbazones (II): These were prepared by the usual condensation of appropriate aromatic aldehydes with 4-arylthiosemicarbazides and were recrystallised from EtOH as shining yellowish needles.

2-Aryl-3-(3-arylthioureido)-4-thiazolidinones (III): To a well stirred solution of II (0.1 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added mercaptoacetic acid (0.15 mole). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr on a water bath. The clear solution was allowed to cool. The crystalline product thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from EtOH.

*5-Aryl-2-arylamino-5-hydrothiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (IV)**: 4-Thiazolidinone (III) (0.01 mole) was treated dropwise with conc. H₂SO₄ (5 ml). The

mixture was cooled and poured into water. After neutralisation with ammonia the desired product (IV) was filtered and recrystallised from EtOH.

5-Aryl-2-arylamino-5-hydrothiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (V)⁵: To 3-thioureido-4-thiazolidinone (III) (0.01 mole) in EtOH (50 ml) was added NaOH (4 N, 5 ml) and then I₂ in KI solution (5%) was added till a permanent tinge of excess of iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr and poured into ice-water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and CS₂ and recrystallised from EtOH.

1,5-Diaryl-5-hydro-2-mercaptothiazolo[3,4-b]-1,2,4-triazoloes (VI)⁶: 3-Thioureido-4-thiazolidinone (III) (0.01 mole) was dissolved in NaOH (4%, 33 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) and refluxed for 2 hr. The resulting mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was adjusted to pH 5-6 with 5 N HCl, and the precipitated solid filtered and recrystallised from EtOH.

The compounds III, IV, V and VI, thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Fungicidal screening: The antifungal activity was evaluated against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari* by usual agar-plate technique⁷ at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations as described earlier⁸. A commercial fungicide,

Dithane M-45, was also tested under similar conditions for comparing the results. The antifungal activity displayed by various compounds is summarised in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

All the tested compounds were significantly toxic to both the test fungi at 1000 ppm but their toxicity was not so spectacular at lower concentrations (100 and 10 ppm) except in case of IVf, Vf, VIe and VI f which inhibited > 50% growth of both the fungi even at 10 ppm and had antifungal activity of the order of Dithane M-45 at 1000 ppm. In general, compounds IV, V and VI were more potent than their parent 3-thioureido-4-thiazolidinones (III). Further, the thiazolo-triazoles (VI) were more active than their thiazolo-oxa(thia)diazole analogues (IV and V).

Although some of the compounds IV, V and VI were considerably toxic to *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* at higher concentration, the overall results are not so encouraging as one would expect from the combined performance of the fused biolabile nuclei. This might be attributed to the partial saturation in the thiazole nucleus resulting in the loss of planarity of the thiazolo-oxa(thia)diazole (IV and V) and thiazolo-triazole (VI) N-bridgehead heterocyclic systems. This presumption is supported by the earlier observations that compact size and planarity of a molecule often enhance its pesticidal activity^{1,6-11}.

It was noted that the presence of chlorine atom in aryl moiety tends to enhance the fungitoxicity, whereas the introduction of methyl group decreases it in such compounds. The fungitoxicity varied but marginally with the fungal species.

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TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING DATA

Compound No. as in Table 1	Average percent inhibition after 96 hr					
	<i>H. oryzae</i>			<i>C. sacchari</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
IIIa	48.6	22.2	9.4	46.4	20.3	8.6
b	54.0	27.1	16.9	53.0	33.2	10.2
c	50.5	24.6	12.5	49.3	30.3	9.2
d	55.1	28.0	17.8	53.1	33.1	11.6
e	60.6	29.3	19.2	59.5	37.2	17.8
f	69.2	38.7	21.3	71.2	40.3	26.5
IVa	54.2	29.2	18.6	58.3	29.0	16.2
b	65.4	41.2	19.7	56.8	30.1	18.5
c	71.6	48.0	16.4	63.5	34.2	19.1
d	78.2	51.2	30.8	77.6	40.2	21.2
e	93.7	60.8	47.8	89.2	58.6	36.4
f	100	63.0	50.4	100	66.1	50.5
Va	51.3	27.8	20.2	55.8	38.2	18.9
b	58.4	39.2	29.8	59.6	41.8	28.3
c	56.2	34.7	18.3	64.3	36.4	16.7
d	60.3	38.6	19.2	70.8	41.5	22.4
e	64.8	39.2	20.3	93.2	63.2	41.6
f	99.2	70.3	50.2	98.9	68.7	51.3
VIa	78.3	39.2	32.6	76.4	41.1	30.4
b	87.2	45.3	34.5	88.1	47.2	34.4
c	80.7	41.6	20.2	94.8	45.3	32.2
d	85.3	56.4	40.5	86.6	57.1	35.6
e	98.7	66.5	51.1	99.2	71.3	50.2
f	100	69.7	53.1	100	72.2	54.0
Dithane M-45 (a com- mercial fungicide)	100	89.0	71.9	100	90.4	73.6

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